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Development of model mesocycles of one - year training of young judokas in the first training year at the stage of primary training

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Abstract

Purpose: Experimental substantiation of the methodology for training young judokas of the first year training at the primary stage by introducing the developed 12 model mesocycles of one-year training.

Methods: Analysis and generalization of scientific and methodological literature, questioning, pedagogical observations, pedagogical testing, pedagogical experiment, methods of mathematical statistics (arithmetic mean, arithmetic mean error, Student's t-test).

Results: Analysis of the increase in the results of young judokas of the experimental group during a one-year training in the first year of training at the stage of primary training showed positive significant differences at a significance level of $p < 0.05$ compared with the increase in the results of judokas in the control group.

Conclusion: The developed 12 model mesocycles of the one-year training of young judokas at the stage of primary training, in combination with various options for constructing microcycles in each model mesocycle, significantly influenced the positive changes in the sports preparedness of young judokas in the first year of training.

Keywords: young judokas, types of mesocycles, types of training microcycles, training methodology, primary training.

Introduction

The mesocycle is a relatively integral stage of the training process lasting from 3 to 6 weeks. Four-week mesocycles are the most popular. Constructing of the training process on the basis of mesocycles makes it feasible to systematize the training process in accordance with the main task of the period or stage of training, to provide the optimal dynamics of loads, the expedient combination of various means and methods of training, the conformity between the factors of pedagogical influence and rehabilitation measures, to achieve the necessary continuity in the development of various qualities and abilities (7; 519 p.).

The purpose of dragging mesocycles is to gradually bring athletes to the effective performance of specific training work. This is achieved by using exercises aimed at developing general and auxiliary physical fitness. In the basic mesocycles, the main work is carried out to improve the functional capabilities of the

main systems of the athlete's body, the development of physical qualities, the formation of technical, tactical and mental preparedness. In the control-preparatory mesocycles, the capabilities of an athlete achieved in previous mesocycles are synthesized (in relation to the specifics of competitive activity), i.e. integral training is carried out. Pre-competitive mesocycles are designed to eliminate minor shortcomings identified during the preparation of the athlete, improving his technical capabilities.

The structure of competitive mesocycles is determined by the specifics of the sport, the features of the sports calendar, the qualification and level of preparedness of the athlete. The recovery mesocycle forms the basis of the transition period and is organized specifically after a tense series of competitions. In some cases, during this mesocycle, it is possible to use exercises aimed at eliminating the manifested shortcomings or tightening physical abilities that are not the main ones for this sport (7; 519 p., 9; 150-152).

It is necessary to distinguish between dragging, basic, control-preparatory, pre-competitive, competitive and restorative mesocycles (5; 97 p., 8; 67-70 p., 9; 150-154 p., 6; 231-237 p.).

For the convenience of designing the mesocycle scheme, the names of their types were conditionally shortened to: dragging mesocycle – DM, basic mesocycle – BM, control-preparatory mesocycle - CPM, pre-competitive mesocycle - PCM, competitive mesocycle - CM and restorative mesocycle - RM.

Materials and methods

For the first year of training, 12 model microcycles were developed, including from 4 to 5 week microcycles of sports training.

As is known, a microcycle is usually understood as a series of training held over several days and providing a comprehensive solution to the tasks at this stage of preparation.

The duration of microcycles can range from 3-4

to 10-14 days. The most common are seven-day microcycles, which, coinciding in duration with the calendar week, are in good agreement with the general mode of life of those involved (7; 518 p.). There are dragging, preparatory, shock, summing, model, competitive and recovery microcycles (9; 144-147 p., 6; 230-231 p., 3; 44-48 p.). Also here, for convenience, the names of

microcycles were conditionally shortened to Dm - dragging microcycle, Pm – preparatory microcycle, Sm – striking microcycle, Mm – model microcycle, Cm – competitive microcycle, Rm - recovery microcycle.

The scheme of construction of the educational and training process of young judokas in the first year of primary training is presented in

Table 2. Results of a survey of parents of 24 schoolchildren engaged in kurash

Months	Mesocy-	Weekly microcycles									
		1	Dm	2	Dm	3	Dm	4	Pm	5	Pm
september - october	DM										
october - november	DM	6	Dm	7	Dm	8	Pm	9	Pm	-	
november - december	BM	10	Pm	11	Pm	12	Pm	13	Rm	14	Dm
december - january	BM	15	Dm	16	Pm	17	Pm	18	Rm	-	
january - february	BM	19	Dm	20	Dm	21	Pm	22	Pm	-	
february - march	CPM	23	Dm	24	Pm	25	Pm	26	Pm	-	
march - april	BM	27	Pm	28	Pm	29	Pm	30	Pm	31	Rm
april - may	CPM	32	Dm	33	Pm	34	Sm	35	Rm	-	
may - june	PCM	36	Pm	37	Pm	38	Pm	39	Mm	40	Mm
june - july	CM	41	Pm	42	Mm	43	Cm	44	Rm	-	
july - august	RM	45	Rm	46	Dm	47	Dm	48	Rm	-	
august	RM	49	Rm	50	Dm	51	Dm	52	Rm	-	

1. dragging mesocycle – DM, basic mesocycle – BM, control-preparatory mesocycle - CPM, pre-competitive mesocycle - PCM, competitive mesocycle - CM and restorative mesocycle - RM.

The construction of the training process for a one-year period for young judokas began in September, which is consistent with the Regulations on sports schools in the Republic of Uzbekistan, funded from the State Budget

of Uzbekistan No. 211 of September 23, 2010, which provides for the beginning of the school year in a sports school from September 2 (1; 88 p.).

Thus, we have developed a one-year training of young judokas in the first training year of the initial training stage with the use of 12 model mesocycles (Figure 1). The first (dragging) mesocycle consisted of five microcycles that are scheduled for September-

October months with the use of 3 dragging and 2 preparatory microcycles. The second (dragging) mesocycle occurs in the months of October-November, where 2 dragging and 2 preparatory microcycles are used. The third (basic) mesocycle is held in November-December, which provides for 3 preparatory and one recovery and dragging microcycles. The fourth (basic) mesocycle covers the months of December-January and consists of a dragging, 2 preparatory and recovery microcycles. In the fifth (basic) mesocycle, further training of novice judokas is provided in January-February, mastering the training loads characteristic of the 2 dragging and 2nd preparatory microcycles. The sixth (control-preparatory) mesocycle consists of the 1st dragging and 3 preparatory microcycles and this cycle is

carried out in February-March months. The seventh (basic) mesocycle falls within the months of March-April, using 4 preparatory and 1 recovery microcycles. The eighth (control and preparatory) mesocycle, where there is one microcycle of the dragging, preparatory, shock and recovery type, and it is carried out in April-May. The ninth (pre-competition) mesocycle falls in the months of May-June with 3 preparatory and two model microcycles. The tenth (competitive) mesocycle is held in June-July, where it is planned to participate in the first competitions of young judokas. This mesocycle provides preparatory, model, competitive and recovery microcycles. The eleventh and twelfth (recovery) mesocycles, 2 recovery and 2 dragging microcycles are used here, which are carried out in July and August.

1 mesocycle

2 mesocycle

3 mesocycle

4 mesocycle

5 mesocycle

6 mesocycle

Figure 1. Model mesocycles of training of young judokas in the first training year of the initial stage of training

In order to express the application of the developed 12 model mesocycles of training of young judokas in the first training year of the primary stage of training on the graph, digital values were conditionally assigned to various microcycles looking as follows: Dm - 2, Pm - 3, Sm - 4, Mm - 5, Cm - 6 and Rm - 1. In the figure, you can see the graphical dynamics of microcycles for 12 model mesocycles.

Results

In order to determine the effectiveness of the developed 12 standard mesocycles of one-year training recommended for young judokas, a special experiment was conducted in the children's and youth sports school No. 1 of the Mirabad district of Tashkent city in the period from September 2, 2020 to August 31, with the

involvement of novice judokas 9-10 years old. The gains in the results of sports training of young judokas of the control (n=23) and experimental (n=22) groups were compared. The dynamics of the increments in the indicators of sports fitness of the experimental and control groups during the year of classes is shown in Table 2.

Table 2 shows that the results of a one-year training of judokas at the primary training stage showed positive changes in the control and experimental groups.

In the 60 m run, the increase in the indicators of young judokas of the control group was: -0.49 ± 0.07 s., of the experimental group: -1.08 ± 0.14 s. The comparison according to the Student's t-test between the control and experimental groups was 2.36 with $p < 0.05$ in favor of the experimental group.

Table 2. Dynamics of increases in indicators of sports readiness of the experimental and control groups during the year of training

Indicators	CG (n=23)		EG (n=22)		t	P
	X	±σ	X	±σ		
Running at 60 m, s	-0,49	0,07	-1,08	0,14	2,36	<0,05
Standing long jump, cm	11,38	1,30	19,41	3,1	2,22	<0,05
Bending the arms in an emphasis lying, times	8,32	1,15	13,26	2,01	2,19	<0,05
Pull-ups on the bar, times	4,18	0,87	6,23	1,1	2,31	<0,05
Five-time throws through the back, s	-2,80	0,34	-4,1	0,21	2,43	<0,05
Ten-time continuous execution	-1,30	0,20	-3,8	0,47	2,28	<0,05

The increase in performance in standing long jumps according to the traditional method in the control group of young judokas was 11.38 ± 1.30 centimeters, and in the experimental group it was 19.41 ± 3.1 centimeters. The increase in results for t was $=2.22$ at $p < 0.05$.

An increase in the results of bending the arms in the lying position and pulling up was also observed in both groups, and the dynamics of the experimental group's indicators was also significant according to Student's t -test: $t=2.19$ at $p < 0.05$ and $t=2.31$ at $p > 0.05$.

Comparison of the gains in results in five-time throws over the back and ten-time continuous executions of "uchi-komi" between the control and experimental groups showed positive and significant shifts in the experimental group with a statistical level of $p < 0.05$. Student's t -test scores in five-time throws over the back were for $t=2.43$, in ten-time continuous executions of "uchi-komi" - $t=2.28$.

Thus, the 12 model mesocycles of training of young judokas proposed in this paper in the first training year of primary training can significantly increase their effectiveness over a one-year period of training.

Conclusion

Developed 12 model mesocycles, consisting of dragging, basic, control-preparatory, pre-competitive, competitive, recovery mesocycles of a one-year training of young judokas at the stage of primary training in combination with various options for building microcycles in each model mesocycle, including dragging, pre-

paratory, striking, model, competitive, recovery microcycles had a positive effect on significant changes in the athletic fitness of young judokas.

One of the most effective ways to further improve the methodology of the training process at the stages of training judoists is to further study and conduct in-depth studies of various combinations of types of microcycles and mesocycles in the context of years of training

References

- Postanovlenie Kabineta Ministrov Respubliki Uzbekistana № 211 ot 23 sentyabrya 2010 goda «O dal'nejshem sovershenstvovanii deyatelnosti sportivnyh shkol i sistemy material'nogo stimulirovaniya truda trenerov i specialistov sportivnyh shkol» [Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 211 dated September 23, 2010 "On further improvement of the activities of sports schools and the system of material incentives for the work of coaches and specialists of sports schools"] (2010) Sobranie zakonodatel'stva Respubliki Uzbekistan, no 38, pp. 76-102. (in Russian).
- Ashmarin B.A. (1978) *Teoriya i metodika pedagogicheskikh issledovanij v fizicheskom vospitanii* [Theory and methods of pedagogical research in physical education] (posobie dlya studentov, aspirantov i prepod. in-tov fiz. kul'tury). Moscow, Fizkul'tura i sport, pp. 223. (in Russian).
- Bayazitov K.F. (2021) Upravlenie uchebno-trenirovochnym processom na razlichnyh etapah mnogoletnej podgotovki tyazheloatletov [Management of the training process at various stages of long-term training of weightlifters] *Fansportga*. [Science to sport], no 2. pp. 44-48. (in Russian).
- Kerimov F.A. (2019) *Nauchnye issledovaniya v sporte* [Scientific research in sports] Tashkent. Ilmiy

- texnika axboroti-press nashriyoti, pp. 264. (in Russian).
- Nikitushkin V.G. (2009) *Sovremennaya podgotovka yunyh sportsmenov* [Modern training of young athletes]: metodicheskoe posobie. Moscow: MKPCN, pp. 113. (in Russian).
- Matveev L.P. (1977) *Osnovy sportivnoj trenirovki*: [Fundamentals of sports training] ucheb. posobie dlya institutov fizicheskoy kul'tury. Moscow: «Fizkul'tura i sporta», pp. 271. (in Russian).
- Platonov V.N. (2004) *Sistema podgotovki sportsmenov v olimpijskom sporte. Obshchaya teoriya i ee prakticheskie prilozheniya* [The system of training athletes in Olympic sports. General theory and its practical applications]. uchebnik dlya studentov vyssh. ucheb. zaved. fizich. vospitaniya i sporta. Kiev: Olimpijskaya literatura, pp. 808. (in Russian).
- Rubin V.S. (2004) *Olimpijskie i godichnye cikly trenirovki. Teoriya i praktika*. (Olympic and annual training cycles. Theory and practice.) Moscow: Sovetskij sport, pp. 188. (in Russian)
- Novickij P.I., Sinyutich A.A. (2019) *Teoriya sporta: kurs lekcij* [Theory of sports: a course of lectures] Vitebsk: VGU imeni P.M.Masherova, pp. 195. (in Russian).
- Arslanov Sh.A., Tangriyev A.J. (2017) *Sport pedagogik mahoratini oshirish (dzyudo)* [Improving sports pedagogical skills-judo] textbook. Toshkent: O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashriyoti, pp. 188. (in Uzbek).

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